

**ON BINOMIAL COEFFICIENTS ASSOCIATED WITH SIERPIŃSKI
AND RIESEL NUMBERS**

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Abstract

In this paper, we investigate the existence of Sierpiński numbers and Riesel numbers as binomial coefficients. We show that for any odd positive integer r , there exist infinitely many Sierpiński numbers and Riesel numbers of the form $\binom{k}{r}$. Let $S(x)$ be the number of positive integers r satisfying $1 \leq r \leq x$ for which $\binom{k}{r}$ is a Sierpiński number for infinitely many k . We further show that the value $S(x)/x$ gets arbitrarily close to 1 as x tends to infinity. Generalizations to base a -Sierpiński numbers and base a -Riesel numbers are also considered. In particular, we prove that there exist infinitely many positive integers r such that $\binom{k}{r}$ is simultaneously a base a -Sierpiński and base a -Riesel number for infinitely many k .

1. Introduction

In 1956, Riesel [11] showed that if $k \equiv 509203 \pmod{1184810}$, then for any natural number n , the value $k \cdot 2^n - 1$ is composite. Today we say that k is a Riesel number if k is an odd positive integer such that $k \cdot 2^n - 1$ is composite for all natural numbers n . Using methods similar to Riesel, Sierpiński [12] showed in 1960 that there are infinitely many odd positive integers k such that $k \cdot 2^n + 1$ is composite for all natural numbers n ; values of k satisfying this property are now known as Sierpiński numbers.

In 2003, Chen [5] showed that if $r \not\equiv 0, 4, 6, 8 \pmod{12}$, then there exist infinitely many odd positive integers k such that k^r is a Sierpiński number. Chen’s result was later extended by Filaseta, Finch, and Kozek [7] for all positive integers r . In their article, Filaseta, Finch, and Kozek asked the following question.

Question 1. Let $f \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$. Does there exist an integer k such that $f(k)$ is a Sierpiński number?

This question has been studied by various authors. For example, Finch, Harrington, and Jones [8] studied this question for $f(x) \in \{x^r + x + c, ax^r + c, x^r + 1, x^r + x + 1\}$ and Emadian, Finch-Smith, and Kallus [6] studied this question for $f(x) = 384x^3 + 432x^2 + 112x - 5$. Other authors considered Question 1 for polynomials $f \in \mathbb{Q}[x]$. Of particular note is the existence of infinitely many Sierpiński numbers in the sequence of triangular numbers and other polygonal numbers. Recall that for $s \geq 3$, the x -th s -gonal number is given by

$$P_s(x) = \frac{s-2}{2}x^2 - \frac{s-4}{2}x.$$

Question 1 with respect to $P_s(x)$ has been studied by Baczkowski et al. [2] and Baczkowski and Eitner [3].

In this article, we study Question 1 with respect to the polynomial

$$\binom{x}{r} = \frac{x(x-1)(x-2)\cdots(x-(r-1))}{r!}$$

where r is a fixed positive integer. Notice that the case $\binom{x}{2}$ has been previously studied since $\binom{x}{2} = P_3(x-1)$. Of course, $\binom{x}{r}$ is more commonly referred to as the *binomial coefficient* function. We begin our investigation on the existence of Sierpiński binomial coefficients for general r in Section 3, and extend some of these results to base a -Sierpiński and a -Riesel binomial coefficients in Section 4.

2. Preliminary Results, Definitions, and Notation

Throughout this article, we use $[a, b]$ to denote the set of integers x such that $a \leq x \leq b$.

For our investigation, we will make use of the following concept, originally introduced by Erdős.

Definition 1. A *covering system* of the integers is a finite collection of congruences such that every integer satisfies at least one congruence from the set.

In this article, we will primarily use covering systems of the form:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 & \pmod{2^\tau} && \text{where } \tau \text{ is a positive integer} \\ 2^{\ell-1} & \pmod{2^\ell} && \text{for each } 1 \leq \ell \leq \tau. \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Many of the proofs in this article rely heavily on the following two theorems, originally due to Zsigmondy [13] and Lucas [10], respectively.

Theorem 2 (Zsigmondy’s Theorem). *Let a and b be relatively prime positive integers with $a > b$. Then for any integer $n \geq 2$, there exists a prime p such that p divides $a^n - b^n$ and p does not divide $a^{\tilde{n}} - b^{\tilde{n}}$ for any $\tilde{n} < n$, with the exceptions*

- $(a, b) = (2, 1)$ and $n = 6$; and
- $a + b$ is a power of 2 and $n = 2$.

Theorem 3 (Lucas’ Theorem). *Let p be a prime, and let m and n be nonnegative integers. Let the base p representations of m and n be $m = \sum_{i=0}^j m_i p^i$ and $n = \sum_{i=0}^j n_i p^i$, respectively, where $m_i, n_i \in [0, p - 1]$ for all $i \in [0, j]$. Then*

$$\binom{m}{n} \equiv \prod_{i=0}^j \binom{m_i}{n_i} \pmod{p}.$$

3. Sierpiński Binomial Coefficients

Lemma 1. *Let p be a prime, and let r be a nonnegative integer. Let j be the smallest nonnegative integer such that $r < p^{j+1}$. Then for all positive integers k such that $k \equiv r \pmod{p^{j+1}}$, we have*

$$\binom{k}{r} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}.$$

Proof. Let the base p representations of r and k be $r = \sum_{i=0}^{j'} r_i p^i$ and $k = \sum_{i=0}^{j'} k_i p^i$, respectively, where $j \leq j'$, $k_i = r_i \in [0, p - 1]$ for all $i \in [0, j]$, $r_i = 0$ for all $i \in [j + 1, j']$, and $k_i \in [0, p - 1]$ for all $i \in [j + 1, j']$. By Theorem 3,

$$\binom{k}{r} \equiv \left(\prod_{i=0}^j \binom{k_i}{r_i} \right) \left(\prod_{i=j+1}^{j'} \binom{k_i}{r_i} \right) \equiv \left(\prod_{i=0}^j \binom{r_i}{r_i} \right) \left(\prod_{i=j+1}^{j'} \binom{k_i}{0} \right) \equiv 1 \pmod{p}.$$

□

The following three lemmas are verified computationally by Mathematica. The code for these lemmas is included in Appendix A, Appendix B, and Appendix C, respectively.

Lemma 2. *Let $p = 641$, and let*

$$\mathcal{G} = \{\gamma \in [1, p - 1] : \gamma \text{ is odd}\} \cup \{2, 6, 8, 10, 12, 22, 24, 30, 32, 34, 44, 46, 48, 52, 56, 66, 70, 74, 80, 84, 86, 94, 100, 102, 104, 110, 118, 120, 134, 136, 140, 144, 146, 160, 162, 174, 176, 182, 184, 190, 194, 198, 200, 202, 208, 222, 224, 236, 248, 250, 252, 260, 270, 292, 294, 304, 312, 318, 334, 336, 338, 348, 366, 368, 374, 402, 414, 424, 426, 454, 474, 530, 546, 552, 578\}.$$

Then there exists a function $\kappa : \mathcal{G} \rightarrow [0, p - 1]$ such that for every $r \in \mathcal{G}$,

$$\binom{\kappa(r)}{r} \equiv -1 \pmod{p}.$$

Lemma 3. *Let $p = 641$. Recall \mathcal{G} defined in Lemma 2. Then there exist a function $\tilde{\kappa} = (\tilde{\kappa}', \tilde{\kappa}'') : [1, 515]^2 \rightarrow [0, p - 1]^2$ such that for every ordered pair $(r', r'') \in [1, 515]^2$,*

$$\binom{\tilde{\kappa}'(r', r'')}{r'} \binom{\tilde{\kappa}''(r', r'')}{r''} \equiv -1 \pmod{p}.$$

Lemma 4. *Let \mathcal{P} be the following set of primes p that divides $2^{2^{\tau-1}} + 1$ for some $\tau \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $(2^{2^{\tau-1}} + 1) / p$ is divisible by another prime distinct from p :*

$$\{641, 114689, 274177, 319489, 974849, 2424833, 6700417, 13631489, 26017793, 45592577, 63766529\}.$$

Then for every $r \in [1, 640]$, there exists $p \in \mathcal{P}$ and $k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\binom{k}{r} \equiv -1 \pmod{p}.$$

Lemma 5. *Let $p = 641$. Recall \mathcal{G} and κ defined in Lemma 2, and recall $\tilde{\kappa} = (\tilde{\kappa}', \tilde{\kappa}'')$ defined in Lemma 3. Let r be a nonnegative integer with base p representation $r = \sum_{i=0}^j r_i p^i$, where $r_i \in [0, p - 1]$ for all $i \in [0, j]$.*

- (a) *If there exists $i_0 \in [0, j]$ such that $r_{i_0} \in \mathcal{G}$, then for all positive integers k such that $k \equiv r + (\kappa(r_{i_0}) - r_{i_0})p^{i_0} \pmod{p^{j+1}}$, we have*

$$\binom{k}{r} \equiv -1 \pmod{p}.$$

(b) If there exist $i_1, i_2 \in [0, j]$ such that $r_{i_1}, r_{i_2} \in [1, 515]$, then for all positive integers k such that $k \equiv r + (\tilde{\kappa}'(r_{i_1}, r_{i_2}) - r_{i_1})p^{i_1} + (\tilde{\kappa}''(r_{i_1}, r_{i_2}) - r_{i_2})p^{i_2} \pmod{p^{j+1}}$, we have

$$\binom{k}{r} \equiv -1 \pmod{p}.$$

Proof. (a) Let the base p representation of k be $k = \sum_{i=0}^{j'} k_i p^i$, where $j \leq j'$, $k_i = r_i$ for all $i \in [0, j] \setminus \{i_0\}$, $k_{i_0} = \kappa(r_{i_0})$, and $k_i \in [0, p - 1]$ for all $i \in [j + 1, j']$. Furthermore, define $r_i = 0$ for all $i \in [j + 1, j']$. By Theorem 3,

$$\begin{aligned} \binom{k}{r} &\equiv \left(\prod_{i=0}^j \binom{k_i}{r_i} \right) \left(\prod_{i=j+1}^{j'} \binom{k_i}{r_i} \right) \equiv \left(\prod_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \neq i_0}}^j \binom{r_i}{r_i} \right) \binom{\kappa(r_{i_0})}{r_{i_0}} \left(\prod_{i=j+1}^{j'} \binom{k_i}{0} \right) \\ &\equiv -1 \pmod{p}. \end{aligned}$$

(b) Let the base p representation of k be $k = \sum_{i=0}^{j'} k_i p^i$, where $j \leq j'$, $k_i = r_i$ for all $i \in [0, j] \setminus \{i_1, i_2\}$, $k_{i_1} = \tilde{\kappa}'(r_{i_1}, r_{i_2})$, $k_{i_2} = \tilde{\kappa}''(r_{i_1}, r_{i_2})$, and $k_i \in [0, p - 1]$ for all $i \in [j + 1, j']$. Furthermore, define $r_i = 0$ for all $i \in [j + 1, j']$. By Theorem 3,

$$\binom{k}{r} \equiv \left(\prod_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \notin \{i_1, i_2\}}}^j \binom{r_i}{r_i} \right) \binom{\tilde{\kappa}'(r_{i_1}, r_{i_2})}{r_{i_1}} \binom{\tilde{\kappa}''(r_{i_1}, r_{i_2})}{r_{i_2}} \left(\prod_{i=j+1}^{j'} \binom{k_i}{0} \right) \equiv -1 \pmod{p}.$$

□

Theorem 4. Let $p = 641$, and recall \mathcal{G} defined in Lemma 2. Let r be a nonnegative integer with base p representation $r = \sum_{i=0}^j r_i p^i$, where $r_i \in [0, p - 1]$ for all $i \in [0, j]$, such that at least one of the following conditions is satisfied:

- (i) there exists $i_0 \in [0, j]$ such that $r_{i_0} \in \mathcal{G}$; or
- (ii) there exists $i_1, i_2 \in [0, j]$ such that $r_{i_1}, r_{i_2} \in [1, 515]$.

Then there exist infinitely many positive integers k such that $\binom{k}{r}$ is a Sierpiński number.

Proof. Let $p_0 = 641$, $p_1 = 3$, $p_2 = 5$, $p_3 = 17$, $p_4 = 257$, $p_5 = 65537$, and $p_6 = 6700417$. Note that for each $\ell \in [1, 6]$,

$$p_\ell \mid 2^{2^\ell} - 1 \text{ and } p_\ell \nmid 2^{2^{\tilde{\ell}}} - 1 \text{ for any } \tilde{\ell} < \ell,$$

so we also have $2^{2^{\ell-1}} \equiv -1 \pmod{p_\ell}$.

Consider the covering system in Equation (1) with $\tau = 6$. Suppose that $n \equiv 2^{\ell-1} \pmod{2^\ell}$ for some $\ell \in [1, 6]$. Then

$$2^n = \left(2^{2^\ell}\right)^t \cdot 2^{2^{\ell-1}} \equiv 1^t \cdot (-1) \equiv -1 \pmod{p_\ell}$$

for some nonnegative integer t . Hence,

$$\binom{k}{r} \cdot 2^n + 1 \equiv -\binom{k}{r} + 1 \pmod{p_\ell}.$$

Let j_ℓ be the smallest nonnegative integer such that $r < p_\ell^{j_\ell+1}$ for each $\ell \in [1, 6]$. By Lemma 1, if

$$k \equiv r \pmod{p_\ell^{j_\ell+1}}, \tag{2}$$

then $\binom{k}{r} \cdot 2^n + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p_\ell}$.

Since Equation (1) is a covering system, if $n \not\equiv 2^{\ell-1} \pmod{2^\ell}$ for any $\ell \in [1, 6]$, then $n \equiv 0 \pmod{2^6}$. Note that $p_0 \mid 2^{2^6} - 1$, so $2^n \equiv 1 \pmod{p_0}$ and

$$\binom{k}{r} \cdot 2^n + 1 \equiv \binom{k}{r} + 1 \pmod{p_0}.$$

Let j_0 be the smallest nonnegative integer such that $r < p_0^{j_0+1}$. Recall the function κ defined in Lemma 2. By Lemma 5(a), if condition (i) of this theorem is satisfied and

$$k \equiv r + (\kappa(r_{i_0}) - r_{i_0})p_0^{j_0} \pmod{p_0^{j_0+1}}, \tag{3}$$

then $\binom{k}{r} \cdot 2^n + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p_0}$.

Hence, for any natural number n , if the congruence in Equation (2) is satisfied for each $\ell \in [1, 6]$ and the congruence in Equation (3) is satisfied, then $\binom{k}{r} \cdot 2^n + 1$ is divisible by some prime p_ℓ with $0 \leq \ell \leq 6$. Using Lemma 1, we ensure that $\binom{k}{r}$ is odd by further requiring $k \equiv r \pmod{2^{j+1}}$, where j is the smallest nonnegative integer such that $r < 2^{j+1}$. By the Chinese remainder theorem, there are infinitely many such integers k . Choosing k so that $\binom{k}{r} \geq p_6$ ensures that $\binom{k}{r}$ is a Sierpiński number.

If condition (ii) of this theorem is satisfied, then the same argument applies by replacing Lemma 5(a) and Equation (3) with Lemma 5(b) and the congruence

$$k \equiv r + (\tilde{\kappa}'(r_{i_1}, r_{i_2}) - r_{i_1})p_0^{j_1} + (\tilde{\kappa}''(r_{i_1}, r_{i_2}) - r_{i_2})p_0^{j_2} \pmod{p_0^{j_0+1}}.$$

□

The following corollary follows from Theorem 4(i) since every odd positive integer must have an odd digit in its base p representation.

Corollary 1. *Let r be an odd positive integer. Then there exist infinitely many positive integers k such that $\binom{k}{r}$ is a Sierpiński number.*

There are 245 integers $r \in [1, 2563]$ that do not satisfy the conditions in Theorem 4. Nonetheless, we can tackle these values of r in the following theorem.

Theorem 5. *Let $r \in [1, 2563]$. Then there exist infinitely many positive integers k such that $\binom{k}{r}$ is a Sierpiński number.*

Proof. If $r \in [641, 2563]$, then the conclusion follows from Theorem 4(i) since the base p representation of r contains the digits 1, 2, or 3, which are in \mathcal{G} defined in Lemma 2.

Suppose that $r \in [1, 640]$. Let \mathcal{P} be the set of primes defined in Lemma 4. By Lemma 4, there exist $p_0 \in \mathcal{P}$ and $k' \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\binom{k'}{r} \equiv -1 \pmod{p_0}$. By the definition of \mathcal{P} , there is some integer $\tau \geq 5$ and some prime $p_\tau \neq p_0$ such that p_0 and p_τ both divide $2^{2^{\tau-1}} + 1$. Consequently, p_0 and p_τ are both prime factors of $2^{2^\tau} - 1$. By Theorem 2, for each $\ell \in [1, \tau - 1]$, let p_ℓ be a prime such that

$$p_\ell \mid 2^{2^\ell} - 1 \text{ and } p_\ell \nmid 2^{2^{\tilde{\ell}}} - 1 \text{ for any } \tilde{\ell} < \ell,$$

so we also have $2^{2^{\ell-1}} \equiv -1 \pmod{p_\ell}$. Note that p_0 and p_τ are distinct from p_ℓ for all $\ell \in [1, \tau - 1]$. This is because $2^{2^\ell} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_\ell}$, implying that $2^{2^{\tau-1}} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_\ell}$, while $2^{2^{\tau-1}} \equiv -1 \pmod{p_0}$ and $2^{2^{\tau-1}} \equiv -1 \pmod{p_\tau}$.

Consider the covering system in Equation (1). Suppose that $n \equiv 2^{\ell-1} \pmod{2^\ell}$ for some $\ell \in [1, \tau]$. Let j_ℓ be the smallest nonnegative integer such that $r < p^{j_\ell+1}$. Similar to the argument presented in proof of Theorem 4, by Lemma 1, if

$$k \equiv r \pmod{p_\ell^{j_\ell+1}}, \tag{4}$$

then $\binom{k}{r} \cdot 2^n + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p_\ell}$.

Since Equation (1) is a covering system, if $n \not\equiv 2^{\ell-1} \pmod{2^\ell}$ for any $\ell \in [1, \tau]$, then $n \equiv 0 \pmod{2^\tau}$. Note that $r < p_0$, so by the definition of k' , for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$k \equiv k' \pmod{p_0}, \tag{5}$$

we have $\binom{k}{r} \equiv -1 \pmod{p_0}$, which implies that $\binom{k}{r} \cdot 2^n + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p_0}$.

The result follows by letting $k \geq \max\{p_0, p_1, \dots, p_\tau\}$ satisfy the congruence relations in Equation (4) for all $\ell \in [1, \tau]$, Equation (5), and $k \equiv r \pmod{2^{j+1}}$, where j is the smallest nonnegative integer such that $r < 2^{j+1}$. \square

There are $641^2 - 1 = 410880$ one-digit or two-digit positive integers $\overline{r'r''}$ in base 641, and from the code given in Appendix B, only $3771 - 1 = 3770$ of them do not have any solution $(x', x'') \in [0, 640]^2$ for the equation

$$\binom{x'}{r'} \binom{x''}{r''} \equiv -1 \pmod{641}.$$

For a positive integer x , let $S(x)$ be the number of $r \in [1, x]$ such that $\binom{k}{r}$ is a Sierpiński number for infinitely many positive integers k . Then $S(410880)/410880 > 99\%$, and the next theorem addresses $S(x)/x$ as x tends to infinity.

Theorem 6. *The density $S(x)/x$ gets arbitrarily close to 1 as x tends to infinity.*

Proof. Let $p = 641$. Note that the cardinality of \mathcal{G} , which is defined in Lemma 2, is 395. Hence, the number of integers less than p^{j+1} such that no digit comes from \mathcal{G} when expressed in base p is

$$1 - \frac{S(p^{j+1} - 1)}{p^{j+1} - 1} \leq \frac{(p - 395)^{j+1} - 1}{p^{j+1} - 1},$$

which tends to 0 as j tends to infinity. □

4. Generalizations of Sierpiński and Riesel Binomial Coefficients

In 2009, Brunner et al. [1] generalized the concept of a Sierpiński number in the following way.

Definition 2. For a positive integer a , we call a positive integer k an *a-Sierpiński number* if $\gcd(k + 1, a - 1) = 1$, k is not a power of a , and $k \cdot a^n + 1$ is composite for all natural numbers n .

The following is an analogous definition for an *a-Riesel number*.

Definition 3. For a positive integer a , we call a positive integer k an *a-Riesel number* if $\gcd(k - 1, a - 1) = 1$, k is not a power of a , and $k \cdot a^n - 1$ is composite for all natural numbers n .

The next theorem is a generalization of Corollary 1.

Theorem 7. *Let a and r be positive integers such that $a + 1$ is not a power of 2 and r is odd. Further assume that there exists a positive integer τ such that $a^{2^\tau} - 1$ is divisible by distinct primes p_0 and p_τ , where neither p_0 nor p_τ divides $a^{2^{\tilde{\ell}}} - 1$ for any $\tilde{\ell} \in [0, \tau - 1]$. Then each of the following holds:*

- (a) *there exist infinitely many positive integers k such that $\binom{k}{r}$ is an a-Sierpiński number;*
- (b) *there exist infinitely many positive integers k such that $\binom{k}{r}$ is an a-Riesel number.*

Proof. For each $\ell \in [1, \tau]$, let p_ℓ be a prime such that

$$p_\ell \mid a^{2^\ell} - 1 \text{ and } p_\ell \nmid a^{2^{\tilde{\ell}}} - 1 \text{ for any } \tilde{\ell} \in [0, \ell - 1],$$

so we also have $a^{2^{\ell-1}} \equiv -1 \pmod{p_\ell}$. Note that such primes exist by Theorem 2. Let $p_{\tau+1}, p_{\tau+2}, \dots, p_\sigma$ be all the prime factors of $a - 1$. Further let $p_{\sigma+1}$ be a prime factor of a . Note that p_ℓ are all distinct for $\ell \in [0, \sigma + 1]$ since $\gcd(a, a^\ell - 1) = 1$ for all positive integers ℓ . For each $\ell \in [0, \sigma + 1]$, let j_ℓ be the smallest positive integer satisfying $r < p_\ell^{j_\ell+1}$.

Using the Chinese remainder theorem, let k satisfy the following congruences:

$$\begin{aligned} k &\equiv 0 \pmod{p_\ell^{j_\ell}} \text{ for each } \ell \in [\tau + 1, \sigma] \text{ and} \\ k &\equiv r \pmod{p_{\sigma+1}^{j_{\sigma+1}+1}}. \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

It follows from Theorem 3 that $\binom{k}{r} \equiv 0 \pmod{p_\ell}$ for each $\ell \in [\tau + 1, \sigma]$ and $\binom{k}{r} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_{\sigma+1}}$. Consequently, $\gcd\left(\binom{k}{r} - 1, a - 1\right) = \gcd\left(\binom{k}{r} + 1, a - 1\right) = 1$ and $\binom{k}{r}$ is not a power of a .

For each $\ell \in [0, \tau]$, if

$$k \equiv r \pmod{p_\ell^{j_\ell+1}}, \tag{7}$$

then $\binom{k}{r} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_\ell}$ by Lemma 1. Let $\sum_{i=0}^{j_\ell} r_{\ell i} p_\ell^i$ be the base p_ℓ representation of r . Since r is an odd integer, there exists an $i_0 \in [0, j_\ell]$ such that $r_{\ell i_0}$ is odd. By Theorem 3, if

$$k \equiv r + (p_\ell - 1 - r_{\ell i_0}) p_\ell^{i_0} \pmod{p_\ell^{j_\ell+1}}, \tag{8}$$

then $\binom{k}{r} \equiv \binom{p_\ell-1}{r_{\ell i_0}} \equiv -1 \pmod{p_\ell}$.

Consider the covering system in Equation (1). If $n \equiv 2^{\ell-1} \pmod{2^\ell}$ for some $\ell \in [1, \tau]$, then $a^n \equiv -1 \pmod{p_\ell}$, and if $n \equiv 0 \pmod{p_0}$, then $a^n \equiv 1 \pmod{p_0}$. Thus, using the Chinese remainder theorem to choose k so that

- $\binom{k}{r} \geq \max\{p_0, p_1, \dots, p_\tau\}$;
- k satisfies Equation (7) for each $\ell \in [1, \tau]$; and
- k satisfies Equation (8) when $\ell = 0$,

we ensure that for any natural number n , $\binom{k}{r} a^n + 1$ is composite and divisible by p_ℓ for some $\ell \in [0, \tau]$. Similarly, using the Chinese remainder theorem to choose k so that

- $\binom{k}{r} \geq \max\{p_0, p_1, \dots, p_\tau\}$;
- k satisfies Equation (7) when $\ell = 0$; and
- k satisfies Equation (8) for each $\ell \in [1, \tau]$,

we ensure that for any natural number n , $\binom{k}{r} a^n - 1$ is composite and divisible by p_ℓ for some $\ell \in [0, \tau]$. Thus, the proof is finished by recalling that k satisfies the congruences in Equation (6). □

For a positive integer x , let $R(x)$ be the number of $r \in [1, x]$ such that $\binom{k}{r}$ is a Riesel number for infinitely many positive integers k . The following theorem follows similarly to Theorem 6.

Theorem 8. *The density $R(x)/x$ gets arbitrarily close to 1 as x tends to infinity.*

In 2001, Chen [4] introduced the concept of a $(2, 1)$ -primitive m -covering. This concept was extended to the following definition by Harrington [9] in 2015.

Definition 4. A covering system $\mathcal{C} = \{q_\ell \pmod{m_\ell}\}_{\ell=1}^\tau$ is called an (a, b) -primitive m -covering if every integer satisfies at least m congruences of \mathcal{C} and there exist distinct primes p_1, p_2, \dots, p_τ such that for each $\ell \in [1, \tau]$,

$$p_\ell \mid a^{m_\ell} - b^{m_\ell} \text{ and } p_\ell \nmid a^{\tilde{\ell}} - b^{\tilde{\ell}} \text{ for any } \tilde{\ell} < m_\ell.$$

Furthermore, a covering system \mathcal{C} is called an (a, b) -primitive disjoint m -covering if \mathcal{C} is an (a, b) -primitive m -covering that can be partitioned into m disjoint (a, b) -primitive 1-covering systems.

Harrington [9] showed that if a and b are relatively prime integers such that $a + b$ is not a power of 2, then there exists an (a, b) -primitive disjoint 3-covering. Thus, the following theorem provides immediate results when $m = 3$.

Theorem 9. *Let a be a positive integer for which there exists an $(a, 1)$ -primitive m -covering \mathcal{C} . Then there exist infinitely many positive integers r for which each of the following holds:*

- (a) *there exist infinitely many positive integers k such that $\gcd\left(\binom{k}{r} + 1, a - 1\right) = 1$, $\binom{k}{r}$ is not a power of a , and $\binom{k}{r} \cdot a^n + 1$ has at least m distinct prime divisors for all natural numbers n ;*
- (b) *there exist infinitely many positive integers k such that $\gcd\left(\binom{k}{r} - 1, a - 1\right) = 1$, $\binom{k}{r}$ is not a power of a , and $\binom{k}{r} \cdot a^n - 1$ has at least m distinct prime divisors for all natural numbers n ; and*
- (c) *if \mathcal{C} is an $(a, 1)$ -primitive disjoint m -covering, then there exist infinitely many positive integers k such that $\gcd\left(\binom{k}{r} + 1, a - 1\right) = \gcd\left(\binom{k}{r} - 1, a - 1\right) = 1$, $\binom{k}{r}$ is not a power of a , $\binom{k}{r} \cdot a^n + 1$ and $\binom{k}{r} \cdot a^n - 1$ are composite, and each of $\binom{k}{r} \cdot a^n + 1$ and $\binom{k}{r} \cdot a^n - 1$ has at least $\lfloor m/2 \rfloor$ distinct prime divisors for all natural numbers n .*

Proof. Let $\mathcal{C} = \{q_\ell \pmod{m_\ell}\}_{\ell=1}^\tau$ be an $(a, 1)$ -primitive m covering with distinct primes p_1, p_2, \dots, p_τ given by Definition 4. Let $p_{\tau+1}, p_{\tau+2}, \dots, p_\sigma$ be all the prime factors of $a - 1$. Further let $p_{\sigma+1}$ be a prime factor of a . Note that p_ℓ are all

distinct for $\ell \in [1, \sigma + 1]$ due to Definition 4 and that $\gcd(a, a^{\tilde{\ell}} - 1) = 1$ for all positive integers $\tilde{\ell}$.

(a) By the Chinese remainder theorem, there exists a positive integer R such that

$$R \equiv \begin{cases} a^{-q_\ell} \pmod{p_\ell} & \text{for all } \ell \in [1, \tau]; \\ 0 \pmod{p_\ell} & \text{for all } \ell \in [\tau + 1, \sigma]; \\ 1 \pmod{p_{\sigma+1}}. \end{cases} \tag{9}$$

Let J_1 be the smallest nonnegative integer such that $R < p_\ell^{J_1+1}$ for all $\ell \in [1, \sigma + 1]$. Again by the Chinese remainder theorem, there exist infinitely many positive integers $r > R$ such that $r \equiv 1 \pmod{p_\ell^{J_1+1}}$ for all $\ell \in [1, \sigma + 1]$. For each such r , let J_2 be the smallest nonnegative integer such that $r < p_\ell^{J_2+1}$ for all $\ell \in [1, \sigma + 1]$. Once again by the Chinese remainder theorem, there exist infinitely many positive integers $k > r$ such that $k \equiv r + R - 1 \pmod{p_\ell^{J_2+1}}$ for all $\ell \in [1, \sigma + 1]$. For each such k , let J_3 be the smallest nonnegative integer such that $k < p_\ell^{J_3+1}$ for all $\ell \in [1, \sigma + 1]$. For each $\ell \in [1, \sigma + 1]$, let the base p_ℓ representations of R , r , and k be $R = \sum_{i=0}^{J_1} R_{\ell i} p_\ell^i$, $r = 1 + \sum_{i=J_1+1}^{J_2} r_{\ell i} p_\ell^i$, and $k = \sum_{i=0}^{J_1} R_{\ell i} p_\ell^i + \sum_{i=J_1+1}^{J_2} r_{\ell i} p_\ell^i + \sum_{i=J_2+1}^{J_3} k_{\ell i} p_\ell^i$, respectively. By Theorem 3,

$$\binom{k}{r} \equiv \binom{R_{\ell 0}}{1} \left(\prod_{i=1}^{J_1} \binom{R_{\ell i}}{0} \right) \left(\prod_{i=J_1+1}^{J_2} \binom{r_{\ell i}}{r_{\ell i}} \right) \left(\prod_{i=J_2+1}^{J_3} \binom{k_{\ell i}}{0} \right) \equiv R_{\ell 0} \equiv R \pmod{p_\ell}.$$

Therefore, $\gcd\left(\binom{k}{r} + 1, a - 1\right) = 1$ since $\binom{k}{r} + 1 \equiv 1 \pmod{p_\ell}$ for all $\ell \in [\tau + 1, \sigma]$, and $\binom{k}{r}$ is not a power of a since $\binom{k}{r} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_{\sigma+1}}$. Lastly, since \mathcal{C} is an $(a, 1)$ -primitive m covering, for each natural number n , there exist distinct $\ell_1, \ell_2, \dots, \ell_m \in [1, \tau]$ such that $n \equiv q_{\ell_\iota} \pmod{m_{\ell_\iota}}$ for all $\iota \in [1, m]$. Thus, for each $\iota \in [1, m]$,

$$\binom{k}{r} \cdot a^n - 1 \equiv R \left((a^{m_{\ell_\iota}})^t a^{q_{\ell_\iota}} \right) - 1 \equiv a^{-q_{\ell_\iota}} a^{q_{\ell_\iota}} - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p_{\ell_\iota}}$$

for some nonnegative integer t .

(b) This proof resembles the proof of part (a) after replacing Equation (9) by

$$R \equiv \begin{cases} -a^{-q_\ell} \pmod{p_\ell} & \text{for all } \ell \in [1, \tau]; \\ 0 \pmod{p_\ell} & \text{for all } \ell \in [\tau + 1, \sigma]; \\ 1 \pmod{p_{\sigma+1}}. \end{cases}$$

(c) Let \mathcal{C} be partitioned into $\mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2, \dots, \mathcal{C}_m$, where $\mathcal{C}_\lambda = \{q_{\lambda\ell} \pmod{m_{\lambda\ell}}\}_{\ell=1}^{\tau_\lambda}$ for each $\lambda \in [1, m]$, and $\tau_1 + \tau_2 + \dots + \tau_m = \tau$. Let $\{p_{\lambda 1}, p_{\lambda 2}, \dots, p_{\lambda \tau_\lambda} : \lambda \in [1, m]\}$ be given by Definition 4. A similar proof as from part (a) applies after replacing

Equation (9) by

$$R \equiv \begin{cases} a^{-q\lambda\ell} \pmod{p_{\lambda\ell}} & \text{for all } \ell \in [1, \tau_\lambda], \text{ where } \lambda \in [1, \lfloor m/2 \rfloor]; \\ -a^{-q\lambda\ell} \pmod{p_{\lambda\ell}} & \text{for all } \ell \in [1, \tau_\lambda], \text{ where } \lambda \in [\lfloor m/2 \rfloor + 1, m]; \\ 0 \pmod{p_\ell} & \text{for all } \ell \in [\tau + 1, \sigma]; \\ 1 \pmod{p_{\sigma+1}}. \end{cases}$$

□

5. Concluding Remarks

Theorem 7 shows that for any integer $a \geq 2$ and any odd positive integer r , there are infinitely many a -Sierpiński numbers and infinitely many a -Riesel numbers of the form $\binom{k}{r}$. Theorems 4 and 5 show that there are infinitely many Sierpiński numbers of the form $\binom{k}{r}$ for most even positive integers r ; however, it is unknown if there are Sierpiński numbers of the form $\binom{k}{r}$ for an arbitrary even positive integer r . Thus, we present the following conjecture.

Conjecture 1. For any positive integer r , there exist infinitely many positive integers k for which $\binom{k}{r}$ is simultaneously a Sierpiński number and a Riesel number.

We end this section with the following question regarding Catalan numbers. Recall that the k -th Catalan number is $\frac{1}{k+1} \binom{2k}{k}$.

Question 10. Are there infinitely many Catalan numbers that are either Sierpiński numbers or Riesel numbers?

The constructions in this paper rely on fixing a positive integer r prior to finding k values for which $\binom{k}{r}$ is either Sierpiński or Riesel. Hence, a new technique might be required in order to tackle the existence of Sierpiński or Riesel Catalan numbers.

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A. Appendix: Mathematica Code for Lemma 2

```
p = 641;
good = Complement[ Table[
  If[ Or @@ Table[ Mod[Binomial[k, r], p] == p - 1, {k, p - 1}], r],
  {r, 0, p - 1}], {Null}]
```

The output `good` is our desired set \mathcal{G} .

B. Appendix: Mathematica Code for Lemma 3

The variables `p` and `good` are defined in the code given in Appendix A.

```
bad = Complement[ Table[r, {r, 0, p - 1}], good];
badbad = {};
Do[ If[ Not[ Or @@ Flatten[
  Table[ Mod[Binomial[k1, bad[[r1]]] * Binomial[k2, bad[[r2]]], p] == p - 1,
    {k1, p - 1}, {k2, p - 1}]]],
  badbad = Append[badbad, {bad[[r1]], bad[[r2]]}]]],
```

```

{r1, Length[bad]}, {r2, Length[bad]}}];
Or @@ Table[ 1 <= badbad[[i, 1]] <= 515 && 1 <= badbad[[i, 2]] <= 515,
  {i, Length[badbad]}]

```

The variable `badbad` contains all ordered pairs of $(r', r'') \in [0, 640]^2$ that fail to satisfy our desired equation. If we want to further investigate by using `Length[badbad]`, the number of ordered pairs of $(r', r'') \in [0, 640]^2$ that fail to satisfy our desired equation is 3771. However, the final output is `False`, showing that there are no unordered pairs $\{r', r''\} \subseteq [1, 515]$ that fails to satisfy our desired equation.

C. Appendix: Mathematica Code for Lemma 4

```

plist = {641, 114689, 274177, 319489, 974849, 2424833, 6700417, 13631489,
  26017793, 45592577, 63766529};
And @@ Table[Or @@ Table[
  Solve[Product[k - j, {j, 0, r - 1}]/r! == p - 1, k, Modulus -> p] != {},
  {p, plist}], {r, 640}]

```

The output is `True`, showing that every $r \in [1, 640]$ satisfies our desired equation.